

Distribution and Determinants of Out-of-Pocket Expenditures on Healthcare in India: An Empirical Analysis at the State Level

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Abstract

This paper deals with an empirical analysis of the changing pattern of the consumer's out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare and the extent of inequality that prevails in the distribution of healthcare spending among different income groups across major Indian states. Gini Coefficient & Palma Ratio are used to measure the degree of inequality. Factors influencing out-of-pocket health expenses are examined in rural and urban India separately by using pooled regression econometric techniques. National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO), India, consumer expenditure data on healthcare are considered. Inequality in out-of-pocket payments on healthcare appeared as remarkably high as compared to the inequality in aggregate expenditure in every parts of the nation. Significant Rural-urban disparity in the Pattern of expenditure and in the inequality levels exhibited across the Indian states. Income being an indicator of ability-to-pay emerged as the prime factor influencing out-of-pocket payments. Pro-poor health insurance policies, proper health infrastructure and good governance in health management system would be effective and revolutionary to reduce the gap in spending pattern between rural and urban households.

Key Words: *Out-of-Pocket Expenses, Healthcare, Distribution, Inequality, Gini Coefficient, Palma Ratio, Determinants.*

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Introduction

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) emphasised on healthy lives and wellbeing for all the people belonging to any age group in a nation by 2030 (UNDP, 2020). However, rising out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare at the household level emerges as a major hindrance in achieving this goal in most of the developing economies. Over the last few decades, rising healthcare expenses of people have become a major socio-economic issue in India. Healthcare expenditure at the household level consists of all spending on medical care, disease prevention, rehabilitation, health administration & regulations and others. Out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare may be categorised into institutional and non-institutional expenses while receiving services from private or public service providers.

The soaring level of income/expenditure inequality has already been recognised as one of the fundamental problems in India. A high level of inequality is observed in different food and non-food components of consumer expenditure across people belonging to various socio-economic strata (Sen & Das, 2017). Education and healthcare expenses have emerged as inequality-enhancing sources of overall expenditure inequality in India (Sen & Das, 2018). After economic reforms, expenditure on healthcare and education has become more biased towards the rich in our country (Sen & Das, 2018). Income disparities and socio-economic gaps appeared as the main causes of inequalities in household health outcomes in India (Acharya, 2018). Due to the existence of unfathomable inequality in the ability to spend for healthcare, the poorer section of the society is deprived of satisfactory health benefits in India (Baru et al., 2010).

Diversified works have been done on health expenditures and the sources of financing in Indian States (Ghosh, 2011; Sahu & Bharati, 2017; Pandey et al., 2018; Vasudevan, Akkilagunta & Kar 2019). Most of the studies found that the cost of medical treatment in India has increased since the 1990s due to changes in demographic structure and chronic disease patterns. Population above sixty-five years of age is more likely to face catastrophic health expenses due to an increase in the cost of healthcare financing (Lopez-Casasnovas & Saez, 2007). Jayakrishnan et al. (2016) highlighted that over-dependence on the private health sector and poor public health system are the major causes of growing out-of-pocket expenditure in healthcare. Rahman et al. (2013) pointed out that private expenses in both in-patient and out-patient medical care services lead to high healthcare bills resulting in financial catastrophe for the households. Ladusingh, Mohanty & Thangjam, (2018) have reviewed recently the burden of total medical expenditure for non-communicable diseases and reproductive health for women in India. Some works on health expenditures are also available in the context of different foreign countries (Kumar et al., 2015; Kavosi et al.,

2012). Smith, Newhouse & Freeland, (2009) argued that apart from medical technology, aggregate income growth is a key driver of healthcare expenditure growth.

Wagstaff, (2002) in his study focused on socio-economic disparity in health outcomes among poor and non-poor by using concentration index. Many recent studies have attempted to analyze disease-related catastrophic healthcare expenditures (Si et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2015; Piroozi et al., 2020). Mukherjee, Haddad & Narayana (2011) pointed out the vulnerability of lower castes people from healthcare needs in India. Seth & Mohanty (2017) in their study showed that the ability to pay generates immense spending disparities between poor and non-poor for similar healthcare needs. Hooda, (2017) in his study pointed out that the lowest quintile population belongs to the above-poverty line in rural areas are more vulnerable to poverty due to the high out-of-pocket cost of healthcare in India.

Studies so far attempted to assess inequalities in consumer expenditure in aggregate and even across different sources. However, an in-depth analysis of distribution of consumer health expenses across different expenditure strata was carried out to a limited extent in previous studies. Hence, this paper attempts to have an intensive study on out-of-pocket expenditure inequality in major Indian states during the ongoing period of economic reforms. The changes of inequality are examined more deeply during the period 2004-05 and 2011-12. Rural-urban differences are explicitly judged. Factors influencing the out-of-pocket healthcare expenses in India are examined separately for rural and urban regions separately by using cross-section econometric techniques.

Methodology

Measuring Inequality with Gini Coefficient

Gini Coefficient measures the magnitude of distribution of income, wealth or consumption expenditure among individuals who deviates in an economy from an equal distribution (Sen & Foster, 1997). Let $(E_1, E_2, E_3, \dots, E_n)$ denotes the distribution of out-of-pocket health expenditures among n household members in the economy (arranged in non-decreasing order). Gini coefficient measures the degree of inequality among different persons defined as:

$$G = \frac{1}{2n^2\mu} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |E_i - E_j|$$

Where, G = Gini Coefficient, E_i = the health expenses of the i^{th} person and μ = average level of expenditure.

Palma ratio

According to Palma, (2014, 2019) and Palma & Stiglitz (2016), Gini Index is more sensitive to the variation in the middle of the entire income or expenditure distribution and relatively insensitive for the higher income class. Palma (2019) developed a ratio to assess the extent of inequality between the poorest and richest population in a society. Middle and upper-middle-income groups in the developing countries have stable income/expenditure share in the distribution. Moreover, the poorest section is deprived of income, wealth, social and economic opportunities (Sen, 1981). We have used Palma Ratio to measure the level of disparity in out-of-pocket healthcare expenses between the poorest and the richest sections. The formula used to calculate the Palma Ratio is –

$$\delta_p = \frac{S_R}{S_P}$$

Where, S_R is the share of the richest 10 percent of population in per capita health expenditure and S_P is the share of the poorest 40 percent of the population.

Factors influencing the out-of-pocket spending on healthcare

We are also interested to examine the determinants of out-of-pocket spending on healthcare those are the probable source of inequality in health expenditure at the household level in the case of rural and urban regions of India. In order to estimate the impact of different factors on the variations in consumer healthcare spending in India, cross-section econometric techniques are used.

Monthly per capita total expenditure (TE): Monthly per capita overall expenditure is used as a proxy of total monthly income which is an indicator of purchasing power of the households. Higher the overall expenditure level, the expenditure on health is expected to be higher. NSS reports define this variable as –

MPCE = monthly consumption expenditure of household ÷ household size.

Age composition (AGEC): Age composition at the household level is vital for consumer health expenses. The more the old and child age population in a household more will be the health expenses at the household level. The same is true for the economy also. To account the impact of age composition, an age composition index (AGEC) has been formulated as a weighted average of aged population above 65 years and population below 5 years, who have more probability of falling sick. Two-third weight is given to the aged population and one-third to the children below five years.

$$\text{AGEC} = \frac{2}{3} * (\text{population aged 65 and above}) + \frac{1}{3} * (\text{population below 5 years})$$

Poverty ratio (POV): Poverty ratio is the percentage of population, who are living below the poverty line. Secondary Data on this variable has been collected from RBI report. The poverty line in this report is based on Tendulkar method on mixed reference period.

Worker population ratio (WPR): Worker population ratio (WPR) is the number of employed persons or person-days per thousands of population actively participated in the total population (NSSO Report). With the increase in WPR, the capacity to maintain healthcare expenses will be higher.

Female workforce participation (FPR): Female participation in work enhances the capability of the household to pay for more consumer goods (Nayak & Mahanta, 2012). It might also positively affect the expenditure on healthcare.

Rural non-farm employment (RNFE): Rural non-farm employment (RNFE) is the source of supplementary income in an economy. More non-farm employment, more the level of income, more will be the health expenses at the household level.

Literacy rate (LR): Literacy rate is an important socio-economic variable that enhances the ability to pursue information on health, education and nutrients of family members (World Bank, 2021). Hence, higher expenditure on health is expected with the rise in literacy rate in an economy.

Percentage of Higher Secondary Standard Population: The percentage of the population completed higher secondary level is taken as an indicator in rural India to capture the role of higher-level educational attainment. Population completed graduation level (HE) is considered for urban India.

Female-headed household size (FHHS) is considered to assess the gender-specific impact of household headship on out-of-pocket health expenses in urban regions.

Regression models have been specified and estimated through pooled regression method for rural and urban India separately. Four models are specified for rural India by using seven explanatory variables. Each model is designed by controlling confounding variables. Explanatory variables are combined to specify different models to control the problem of multicollinearity.

Econometric Models specified for the rural sector as follows:

$$\text{Model 1: } OP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TE_i + \beta_2 AGE C_i + \beta_3 WPR_i + v_{1i}$$

$$\text{Model 2: } OP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WPR_i + \beta_2 POV_i + \beta_3 HS_i + v_{2i}$$

$$\text{Model 3: } OP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HS_i + \beta_2 FPR_i + \beta_3 RNFE_i + v_{3i}$$

$$\text{Model 4: } OP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 POV_i + \beta_2 RNFE_i + \beta_3 LR_i + v_{4i}$$

To account the influence of different factors on out-of-pocket health expenditure in urban India, five cross-section regression models have been specified by combining nine explanatory variables alternatively. To control the effect of heteroscedasticity, robust standard error has been applied in the regression analysis. Specification tests such as VIF for multicollinearity check and RESET for omitted variables have also been carried out.

Models specified for urban India are as follows:

$$\text{Model 1: } OP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 TE_i + \alpha_2 FHHS_i + \alpha_3 FPR_i + u_{1i}$$

$$\text{Model 2: } OP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 HE_i + \alpha_2 FPR_i + \alpha_3 POV_i + u_{2i}$$

$$\text{Model 3: } OP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 HE_i + \alpha_2 LR_i + \alpha_3 WFPR_i + u_{3i}$$

$$\text{Model 4: } OP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FPR_i + \alpha_2 HE_i + \alpha_3 LR_i + u_{4i}$$

$$\text{Model 5: } OP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 TE_i + \alpha_2 AGE C_i + \alpha_3 FPR_i + u_{5i}$$

Data are collected from 61st and 68th Rounds survey reports on consumer health expenditures, National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) India. Monthly per capita consumer expenditure (MPCE) data of Mixed Reference Period (MRP) for fifteen major Indian states are considered in this empirical study. Data on different explanatory variables are collected from NSSO and other Govt. Official Statistics.

Results & Discussion

Share (Percentage) of Out-of-Pocket Expenditure on Healthcare: Indian States

Consumer out-of-pocket real expenditure on healthcare has increased in India over the years. An increase in healthcare expenses as a share of total expenditure is either due to greater service utilization or due to the higher cost of healthcare services. At the aggregate level, consumers spent 6.27 percent of their total spending on healthcare in 2004-05 which becomes 7.37 percent in 2011-12 in rural India. In urban India, health expenses were 5.20 percent of total expenses in 2004-05 and it has increased to 6.07 percent 2011-12 (Table 1). Health expenditure share has increased in both lowest and highest fractile classes irrespective of rural and urban areas. Interestingly, richer classes in rural regions show a relatively higher share compared to that of urban regions.

Table 1
Share (Percentage) of Out of Pocket Expenditure on Health in India

Area & Time Periods	All Classes	Fractile Classes					
		0-5%	5-10%	10-20%	80-90%	90-95%	95-100%
Rural 2004-05	6.27	2.35	3.33	3.36	7.34	8.44	9.98
Rural 2011-12	7.37	3.37	3.70	4.41	8.18	9.99	12.86
Urban 2004-05	5.20	3.60	4.17	4.85	5.27	5.65	5.68
Urban 2011-12	6.07	3.74	4.26	4.79	6.29	7.10	7.07

Source: Author's calculation from NSSO data.

Disparity in the share of spending on healthcare across different states is depicted in Table 2. Except for Haryana and Madhya Pradesh (MP), thirteen major states of India show an increase in the share of health spending in the rural areas during the period 2004-05 to 2011-12. In 2004-05, rural areas of Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh show a larger share of household medical expenditures than the national average. Kerala has remained at the upper most rank and Assam has remained at the lowest rank in 2011-12. Rural Bihar has exhibited the highest positive change in percentage point and highest drop in share is observed in rural Haryana.

While looking at the urban regions, the share of health expenditure above the national average is observed in Kerala, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh in 2004-05. Orissa has exhibited an upswing in health expenditure share. A decline in the expenditure share is observed in urban regions of Haryana, Kerala and Madhya Pradesh (Table 2). In Haryana, insurance coverages such as ESI and Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) were extended to different segments of population including workers of unorganized sectors, who were largely benefitted to reduce their out-of-pocket healthcare costs (DESA Haryana, 2012). This might be a reason for declining expenditure share in this state.

Table 2
Share (Percentage) of Out-of-Pocket Expenditure on Health: Indian States

States	Rural			Urban		
	2004-05	2011-12	Change in Share	2004-05	2011-12	Change in Share
Andhra Pradesh	6.55	8.52	1.97	4.93	5.88	0.95
Assam	1.97	2.75	0.78	2.81	3.96	1.15

Bihar	3.05	5.56	2.51	3.50	4.72	1.21
Gujarat	5.47	5.89	0.42	5.00	5.03	0.03
Haryana	5.62	4.83	-0.79	4.50	4.20	-0.30
Karnataka	4.16	6.50	2.33	3.73	5.23	1.50
Kerala	9.87	10.31	0.44	9.03	8.85	-0.18
Madhya Pradesh	6.81	6.44	-0.36	5.26	5.12	-0.13
Maharashtra	7.44	8.63	1.19	6.55	6.80	0.24
Orissa	5.18	6.59	1.41	3.97	6.82	2.85
Punjab	6.95	9.25	2.30	5.01	6.60	1.59
Rajasthan	5.19	6.30	1.11	5.05	4.85	-0.20
Tamil Nadu	6.20	7.98	1.79	4.61	6.29	1.67
Uttar Pradesh	8.42	9.74	1.32	5.81	6.90	1.09
West Bengal	6.89	7.99	1.10	6.68	8.49	1.81
All India	6.27	7.37	1.09	5.20	6.07	0.88

Source: Author's calculation from NSSO data.

Inequality in Out-of-Pocket Healthcare Expenses: Indian States

A wide disparity in consumer health expenses is observed among different sections of population in India (Table 1). It is also true at the regional level. Our interest is to examine the degree of inequality and its change in India and its major constituent states during the period 2004-05 to 2011-12. To estimate the degree of inequality in the distribution of healthcare expenses, Gini-coefficient (G) has been used.

Table 3
Inequality in Consumer Health Expenses in the Indian States: Gini Coefficient

States	Gini Coefficient (G)			
	Rural		Urban	
	2004-05	2011-12	2004-05	2011-12
Andhra Pradesh	0.468	0.442	0.387	0.442
Assam	0.300	0.358	0.342	0.421
Bihar	0.341	0.380	0.442	0.362
Gujrat	0.373	0.449	0.331	0.373
Haryana	0.306	0.338	0.432	0.332
Karnataka	0.400	0.478	0.364	0.466
Kerala	0.351	0.454	0.256	0.467
Madhya Pradesh	0.446	0.465	0.468	0.41
Maharashtra	0.436	0.495	0.433	0.445
Orissa	0.438	0.454	0.389	0.472

Punjab	0.408	0.424	0.375	0.366
Rajasthan	0.402	0.396	0.237	0.365
Tamil Nadu	0.554	0.499	0.385	0.386
Uttar Pradesh	0.385	0.478	0.377	0.485
West Bengal	0.449	0.474	0.481	0.531
All India	0.448	0.474	0.392	0.448

Source: Authors' Calculation from NSSO data.

Health expenditure distribution across different classes is more unequal in rural areas compared to that of urban areas in India. In most of the states, the degree of inequality has increased in the rural areas during the period 2004-05 to 2011-12 (Table 3). Rural Tamil Nadu shows the highest level of inequality followed by Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal and Madhya Pradesh in 2004-05. Inequality is relatively low in the rural areas of Assam, Haryana and Bihar. In 2011-12, inequality has dropped in Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu. Almost all the States exhibit an increase in inequality in rural out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare services.

Urban regions of West Bengal show the most unequal distribution of out-of-pocket health expenses in both the time points. Urban regions of Rajasthan, Kerala and Gujarat show low level of inequality in consumer health expenditure. Most of the states experienced a rise in inequality levels except Bihar, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh and Punjab in 2011-12 (Table 3). Gini Coefficient takes into account the expenditure differences among all the persons belonging to different expenditure classes. Since Gini index is insensitive to the extreme fractile groups of the distribution, we have estimated Palma ratio to examine the level of disparity between the lowest and highest population classes. Among twelve fractile classes of expenditure, the lowest five fractile classes represent the bottom 40 percent of all population and top two fractile classes represent the richest 10 percent.

Table 4
Disparity in Out-of-pocket Health Expenses between Lower and Upper Classes: Palma Ratio

States	Palma Ratio (δ_p)			
	Rural		Urban	
	2004-05	2011-12	2004-05	2011-12
Andhra Pradesh	2.63	2.23	1.23	2.52
Assam	2.05	1.39	1.28	2.05
Bihar	1.26	1.72	2.90	1.33
Gujarat	1.89	2.50	1.53	1.56
Haryana	1.69	1.43	2.34	1.53

Karnataka	1.76	3.00	1.66	2.52
Kerala	2.50	2.40	0.74	2.95
Madhya Pradesh	3.45	2.54	2.96	1.93
Maharashtra	2.55	3.18	2.38	2.35
Orissa	1.76	2.60	1.22	2.81
Punjab	3.49	2.33	2.26	1.63
Rajasthan	2.42	1.78	1.15	1.8
Tamil Nadu	5.50	3.22	1.81	1.77
Uttar Pradesh	1.28	2.99	1.60	3.08
West Bengal	2.96	2.75	3.85	4.16
All India	2.37	2.81	1.82	2.52

Source: Authors' calculation from NSSO data.

The richest 10 percent of rural households spend more than twice the spending of the poorest 40 percent on healthcare services in India on an average (Table 4). Difference in rural out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare between these two groups is highest in Tamil Nadu followed by Punjab and Madhya Pradesh in 2004-05. Rural Bihar shows lowest disparity level. Inequality measured in terms of Palma Ratio is lower in Utter Pradesh, Haryana, Karnataka and Orissa ($\delta_p < 2$) in 2004-05. However, in 2011-12, rural Tamil Nadu has the maximum level of inequality between the richest and the poorest groups. Decline in inequality between extreme groups are observed in the rural regions of Maharashtra, Karnataka, Utter Pradesh, Orissa, Gujrat and Bihar.

Urban West Bengal shows the highest disparity in out-of-pocket expenditure of the richest 10 percent and bottom 40% population. The lowest inequality level is observed in Kerala followed by Rajasthan, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh and Assam. The ratio has increased in most of the states indicating higher rise in richest 10 percent population relative to that of bottom 40 percent population (Table 4).

Determinants of Consumer Out of Pocket Expenditure on Healthcare

Pooled regression techniques are followed to estimate the models specified for rural and urban India separately. Cross-section regression results for rural India are depicted in Table 5. Monthly total consumer expenditure and age composition are highly significant to predict the fluctuations in out-of-pocket health expenses in the rural regions of India (Model 1). Poverty ratio has appeared as one of the most significant factors influencing out-of-pocket expenditure on health in opposite direction. Female work participation, attainment of higher secondary level education and rural non-

farm employment show positive and significant effects on consumer health expenditure in rural India. The regression results show that out-of-pocket expenses of healthcare increase with rise in non-farm employment in rural areas (Table 5).

Table 5
Determinants of Out of Pocket Expenditure on Health in Rural India: Regression Results

Dependent variable: <i>Rural Out of Pocket Expenditure on Health (OP)</i>				
Explanatory variables	M1	M2	M3	M4
TE	0.103*** (11.2)			
AGEC	0.908*** (4.13)			
POV		-1.759** (-2.83)		-2.241*** (-3.39)
WPR	0.109 (0.28)	0.092 (0.15)		
FPR			0.947** (2.29)	
LR				0.688 (0.79)
HS		11.416*** (2.87)	15.436*** (4.28)	
RNFE			2.242*** (3.17)	1.133 (1.2)
Constant	-105.179 (-3.94)	64.306 (1.26)	-105.632 (-3.70)	71.151 (1.00)
F statistics	45.23	9.75	11.79	9.25
R-square	0.890	0.672	0.746	0.595
***indicates significance at 1% level, ** at 5% level and * at 10% level, t-values are shown in parentheses.				

Data Source: NSSO data.

Regression results for urban India are shown in Table 6. Total monthly expenditure has emerged as a strong predictor of health expenditure at the individual level in urban areas (Model 1 & Model 5). All the coefficients have plausible signs. The coefficient of AGECE is positive and significant (Model 5) indicates that healthcare cost increases as the population above 65 years and below 5 years rises. Result also shows the negative and significant relationship between poverty and consumer health expenditure. Out-of-pocket expenditure decreases as the poverty level increases in urban regions

since poverty reduce the ability to spend more on healthcare. Literacy rate and higher education both have a significant impact on the dependent variable although the latter is visible to have a greater impact on the dependent variable in urban India.

Table 6
Determinants of Out of Pocket Expenditure on Health in Urban India: Regression Results

Explanatory variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
TE	0.071*** (6.86)				0.079*** (7.14)
FHHS	27.176** (2.14)				
AGEC					1.420*** (2.79)
POV		-4.211*** (-4.6)			
WPR			2.279 (-3.91)		
FPR	3.363** (2.53)	0.115 (0.08)		2.446 (1.46)	0.099 (0.1)
LR			4.196** (2.09)	4.227** (2.55)	
HE		4.478 (1.52)	8.656*** (2.97)	9.013*** (3.12)	
Constant	-156.451 (-2.43)	116.765 (1.8)	-435.159 (-3.91)	-395.595 (-3.34)	
F statistics	40.11	13.74	12.07	9.13	36.03
R-squared	0.823	0.649	0.504	0.518	0.839
Root MSE	27.167	38.257	45.524	44.842	25.91
***indicates significance at 1 % level, ** at 5% level and * at 10% level, t-values are shown in parentheses.					

Source: NSSO Data.

An increase in the share of expenditure on healthcare in total consumer spending is a good sign for a society which signifies that the people give priority to healthcare along with other expenses. However, an increase in healthcare expenses is good unless and until it becomes a financial burden to the households. Moreover, unequal distribution of health expenses among different classes of population is not desirable for a society. It is observed from the data that people having higher spending capacity spend more on

both institutional and non-institutional medical expenses. A high disparity in health expenditures at the consumer level indicates that the richer section can spend adequately to get well treatment, while the poorest section fails to spend more. The poorer section spends less as they cannot pay for the high out-of-pocket cost of healthcare and it is observed in almost all the states.

It is a natural economic phenomenon when household expenditures increase over the years due to escalation in the consumer price indices even when the consumption basket remains unchanged. However, a gap in the spending on healthcare among different fractile classes signifies that all the households are not equally able to spend despite a rise in the average spending. This is not a socially desirable outcome of the health sector from the welfare perspective.

Inequality in the distribution of out-of-pocket expenditure on health at the household level is relatively higher in the rural regions in comparison to the urban region. One possible reason is access to both public and private healthcare facilities, which is more pronounced in urban areas. The choice set is greater for urban people than rural people in terms of the number of public hospitals, pharmacies, diagnostic centres and private visits to doctors for treatment etc. Rural people of India need to travel long distances for accessing tertiary healthcare facilities when such facilities are not available in the neighbourhood of their locality. Additional spending on travel costs, hotel rent, food costs increase the financial burden for treatment at a distant healthcare institution. Severe inequality exists between the richest and poorest sections of the society in terms of per capita healthcare expenses. In some states such as Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Haryana, the inequality level has declined between 2004-05 and 2011-12 irrespective of rural and urban areas. State healthcare policies, standard of living and social infrastructure might be the major sources of inequality variations across states.

The study reveals that monthly per capita expenditure as a proxy of income has turned out to be a strong determinant to influence out of pocket health expenditure irrespective of rural and urban areas. Higher the income, higher is the ability to spend on healthcare needs. Age composition is an important determinant of consumer health expenses in both the rural and urban regions of India. Impact of age composition has emerged as relatively stronger in urban sector. Price paid for healthcare facilities is comparatively higher in urban sector due to higher cost of living. Poverty has a negative impact on out-of-pocket health expenditure as poverty reduces the ability to pay for healthcare facilities in Indian states. As the overall poverty level rises in a state or country, the share of spending on subsistence goods increases, especially among the low-income group. Expenditure on health then becomes luxury consumption to the poorer section in both rural and urban regions. Coefficient of literacy rate is appeared as positive but insignificant. An

increase in the proportion of people completing HS level in a rural region and completing graduation and above in an urban region shows a significant impact on the dependent variable. It is because higher education gives greater awareness about healthcare and enhances the decision-making ability for such spending. FPR emerged as important factor influence health expenditure at the consumer level. Gender effect on family headship and employment has an impact on healthcare costs at the household level.

Concluding Remarks

Consumer out-of-pocket expenditure on healthcare has an upward surge in India over time, yet it has not been equally distributed among the poorest to the richest sections of the society indicating a serious policy gap. Income being an indicator of ability-to-pay emerged as the prime factor influencing out-of-pocket payments irrespective of rural and urban areas. A person with chronic disease in an abjectly poor family does not receive the same level of healthcare services as expected by a similar patient in a rich family in India. The difference in expectation is created due to dissimilarity in capacity-to-pay among households. This inequality creates social deprivation which must be a serious concern of the state to intervene. Therefore, our recommendation is to provide standard healthcare services to all the people belonging to different economic classes, Government should adopt health insurance policies that need to be linked with ability-to-pay. Government expenditure should be a higher percentage of GDP to ensure proper health infrastructure and good governance in health management system. Premiums for health insurance to be provided for adequate healthcare coverage to the poorest section of the Indian society can be a helpful policy in India. Moreover, Government should arrange free health cards, especially for the poor and the disadvantaged to attain hospitalisation free of cost. As state-level variation is strongly observed in India, health policy is required to be formulated to comply with the health expenditure status of different states. If the objective of the government is to reduce the gap in expenses between the poorest and richest section of population at the state level, then Palma ratio gives a better view for decision making. However, Govt. should emphasize the reduction in inequality in out-of-pocket expenditure irrespective of the constituent states.

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